

ENHANCING CAPILLARY PUMPING ON NITROCELLULOSE PAPER BY APPLYING PRESSURE USING AN ELECTROMAGNET

Zitao Feng, Zejingqi Chen, and Weijin Guo
Shantou University, China

ABSTRACT

In this work, we developed a facile method to enhance the capillary pumping on a nitrocellulose test strip by applying pressure on its surface using an electromagnet. The pressure was applied through a hydrophobic PDMS piece contacting the surface of the nitrocellulose test strip. The pressure applied can be easily adjusted by changing the current through the electromagnet. Compared to the control group without pressure, the groups with pressure of current 0, 6, 12, 19, 24 (a.u.) can improve the capillary pumping velocity by 56%, 25%, 12%, 29%, and 76% respectively. It is highly promising to use this method to control capillary pumping velocity on lateral flow tests.

KEYWORDS: nitrocellulose paper, PDMS, electromagnet, lateral flow tests, pressure, capillary pumping velocity

INTRODUCTION

Capillary pumping velocity control on the paper test strip is always an interesting topic for researchers in the field of lateral flow tests, since it has a big influence on the performance of lateral flow immunoassays. Many active and passive methods have been used to increase or decrease the capillary pumping velocity on nitrocellulose test strips [1-4]. However, majority of them need complex experimental setups or do not provide a customized adjustment of pumping velocity. Here, we developed a method to enhance the capillary pumping on nitrocellulose paper with a simple strategy (by applying pressure on nitrocellulose surface using a hydrophobic PDMS piece) and a customized adjustment of pumping velocity (by changing the current through the electromagnet).

EXPERIMENTAL

Figure 1: The design of nitrocellulose test strip (a): the yellow part indicates the position of PDMS contacting nitrocellulose, the schematic of the experimental setup (b), the experimental setup (c), the monitor showing the current (d), and the schematic of electric circuit (e).

As shown in Figure 1(a), we have a nitrocellulose (Vivid 90 Lateral Flow Nitrocellulose Membrane, Pall Corporation) test strip with a loading pad and a fluidic channel, which is fabricated by a laser cutter. The loading pad has a diameter of 10 mm, and the fluidic channel has a dimension of 6×56 mm. Figure 1(b) shows the experimental setup: part of nitrocellulose surface was covered by a hydrophobic PDMS piece, the PDMS piece was glued to an electromagnet (working voltage: DC 5 V, maximum current: 0.3 A, weight: 26.4 g) by double-side tape, and the nitrocellulose test strip was fixed on a magnetic patch by double-side tape. Nitrocellulose paper surface of 10 mm long was covered by a PDMS piece, indicated by yellow color in Figure 1(a). Figure 1(c) is a picture of the real experimental setup. The pressure applied was controlled by the current of the electromagnet, which is shown on a small LED monitor, shown in Figure 1(d). Figure 1(e) is the schematic of the electrical circuit of the electromagnet: the voltage was controlled by Arduino, and the current can be tuned to the desired value using a knob.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the area and volume capacity of nitrocellulose paper, we loaded 60 μL water on the loading pad, and recorded the experiments using a digital camera (Canon EOS RP, Japan). The control group (without PDMS and electromagnet on the nitrocellulose surface), and experimental groups (with PDMS and electromagnet on the nitrocellulose surface, and with current as 0, 6, 12, 19, 24 (a.u.)) are repeated four times. The average times of the total pumping process (from the time when water started contacting nitrocellulose to the time when the test strip was fully filled) for groups with current 0, 6, 12, 19 and 24 (a.u.) are 110, 130, 146, 125, and 93 seconds respectively. For control group, the average total time is 174 seconds. As shown in Figure 2, we can see an obvious increase of capillary pumping velocity on nitrocellulose test strips after applying pressure on part of their surfaces. The increases are 56%, 25%, 12%, 29%, and 76% for current of 0, 6, 12, 19, 24 (a.u.) respectively, shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The comparison of capillary pumping velocities on nitrocellulose paper test strips without or with pressure from an electromagnet.

For the trend of capillary velocity change, we see a decrease when the current change from 0 to 12 (a.u.), and then an increase when the current change from 12 to 24 (a.u.). We think the reason behind the increase of pumping velocity is a combination of two factors. The pressure applied may change the pore size of nitrocellulose paper since the nitrocellulose fibers are soft and may deform under pressure. Another reason is that the PDMS piece increases the surface area to facilitate the capillary pumping. Different factor may dominate the influence on capillary pumping velocity at different current. However, more investigations are needed to be clearer about the physics behind this.

For the future applications of this method, we envision that it can be used for the pumping velocity control of lateral flow tests. The capillary pumping velocity can be easily customized by adjusting the current through the electromagnet. Furthermore, we can easily adjust the contacting area, and change the position of PDMS piece to achieve the goal of capillary velocity control. Dynamic control of capillary velocity during pumping is also possible.

CONCLUSION

An easy method to control the capillary pumping velocities on nitrocellulose test strips is developed in this work. By applying pressure on surface of nitrocellulose paper using an electromagnet, we can increase the capillary pumping velocity by 76% maximally. By adjusting the current through the electromagnet, this method is expected to provide customized capillary pumping velocities on nitrocellulose test strips, which is of great interest for applications of lateral flow immunoassays.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by Shantou University (STU Scientific Research Foundation for Talents: NTF20034).

REFERENCES

- [1] Schaumburg and Berli. *Microfluidics and Nanofluidics* 23.8 (2019): 1-10.
- [2] Channon et al. *Lab on a Chip* 18.5 (2018): 793-802.
- [3] Songok and Toivakka. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 8.44 (2016): 30523-30530.
- [4] Xiao et al. *Micromachines* 12.5 (2021): 562.

CONTACT

* Weijin Guo; guoweijin@stu.edu.cn; Zitao Feng and Zejingqiu Chen contribute equally to this work.